

Role of suppliers' selection on negotiation in oil and gas industry

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Cite this paper as:

Esmacili, Z., Kashir, M., & Izadi, A. (2017, April). *Role of suppliers' selection on negotiation in oil and gas industry*. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Modern Ideas in Engineering, Science and Technology* (Geneva, Switzerland). doi:10.5281/zenodo.17460116

Abstract

Nowadays, many factors affect suppliers' selection, and in this paper, we want to show that technical ability, reputation, quality standards and certificates, distance, experience, and financial power can be important elements for decision-makers in the oil and gas industry. This research was conducted at the South Pars Gas Complex Company in the Middle East. We analyzed 55 questionnaires filled out by South Pars Gas Complex employees, and the results show that quality, as well as technical and financial ability, had more effect on decision-makers.

Keywords: Supply Chain Management, Analysis Hierarchy Process (AHP), Decision making

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Introduction

Larger diversities in demands, improvement in communication and information technology systems, higher competition in global level, changes in governmental regulations as well as initiate of new concepts such as corporate social responsibility has brought the attention of companies towards supply chain management more than ever (Tracey and Tan, 2001, 174). Nevertheless, decreasing the cost of operation while increasing the quality of the services provided for the customer have been known as competitive advantages in this field. Supply Chain Management as a section dealing mostly with these sort of uncertainty, needs to plan and forecast the changes that may occur in this process. Yet it requires a systematic approach with qualitative and quantitative criteria based on scientific techniques. Supplier selection as one of the crucial and complicated activities in Supply Chain Management has likewise attracted many researchers and investigators. Searching for new suppliers, evaluating them, proposing the top alternatives and providing some inputs for the potential collaborative relationship with the supplier are just some examples of the decision that this section have to make (Rodrigues et al, 2014, 194). Nonetheless, the main part of product cost is reflected by the cost of raw materials, elements or even purchased services, considering the high technology companies. This highlights the role of the purchasing department and especially supplier selection activity for influencing the strategic position of the company when it comes to efficiency, productivity and flexibility of the organization (Ghodsypour & Obrein, 2001).

From managerial aspect, selecting the proper level of integration of internal resources with the external supply chain as well as the right degree in sharing the information within the organization are crucial for taking the correct decisions. Improving the business process by finding the boosted inventory level, decreasing the risk in supply chain and the production cost, increasing the profit, and improving the customer satisfaction are the main goals of SCEM

system that aims to facilitate the operation among associates (Apak , Vayvay & Feyzioglu, 2013,293-294).

In order to find a solution for these Multi Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) problem, different methods have been proposed and tested. A classical method is AHP approach, in which the criteria are weighted by a group of expert. Critics to this method is time consuming and low degree of flexibility and adjustability to market changes. Another approach is integrating F-AHP and F-TOPSIS with a set of decision principles. These models have been selected due to the consideration of inter dependences between secondary criteria. Also important to note is that the outcome of the model depends on the inputs provided by the decision makers. The risk of bias of the decision maker towards any alternative need to be considered precisely. It is also recommended to compare the results with the results of other fuzzy MADM methods such as ORESTE, MAUT, SAW, VIKOR, ELECTRE, or PROMETHEE. (Apak,Vayvay & Feyzioglu, 2013, 302). Other have proposed integration of AHP, the Bayesian Classifier Algorithm, and dynamic probabilities (AHP-BCA). This approach uses computer programming and seeks automatically the best value with the greatest probability for each criterion. It is believed to well serve the dynamic market with this approach (F.T.S. Chan, S.H. Chung, J.C.L. Chow, B. Niu, 216). Previous studies have emphasized the importance of identifying supplier selection criteria through analytical models such as AHP (Esmaeili & Kashir, 2013). These studies form part of the existing research related to this topic, and in the following sections, we provide a more detailed discussion on supplier selection and planning after a brief explanation of the problem description.

Problem Description

All firms have their own strategies for supply chain management. They recognize that these strategies affect purchasing decisions, and they strive to reduce costs in

order to offer lower final prices for their products. Xu et al. (2013) stated that, nowadays, corporate social responsibility (CSR) contributes to globalization. In their study, they interviewed several managers from a rubber manufacturing company and ultimately identified seven criteria that managers use when making purchasing decisions.

The aim of this research is to identify and rank the criteria for suppliers' selection by using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) approach in the South Pars Gas Complex in the Middle East.

Analytic hierarchy process (AHP)

The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) was first introduced by Saaty, and this technique is used to measure various factors influencing managers' decision-making. It helps and facilitates decision-making based on judgments, feelings, experiences, memories, and other factors that may influence decisions within multilevel hierarchical structures.

The application of AHP involves four main steps. First, the supplier selection problem is defined and the objective is specified. Second, the criteria and sub-criteria that must be satisfied to achieve the goal are determined. Third, alternative decisions are developed. Finally, a decision is made based on the results (V. Agarwal & Sharma, 2014, p. 102).

Figure 1: (Ryu,2014,74)

Selection of a supplier and planning

The purchasing department seeks to select the best processes and procedures among all available options. Some researchers, such as Van Weele (2010), have noted that companies should find the most effective ways to supply all their products. Similarly, Cavinato et al. (2006) and Pooler et al. (2004) examined the role of purchasing and identified several key aspects of the purchasing process:

- Achieving the best possible purchase with reasonable quality while reducing costs;
- Establishing logical and competitive prices through negotiation and fulfillment of commitments;
- Expanding relationships with sources of supply;
- Ensuring optimal supplier efficiency.

Ultimately, organizations can explore additional options that contribute to improving company performance.

Evaluating the supplier selection process reduces purchasing risks, and all companies should evaluate their suppliers based on essential criteria (Eshtehardian, Ghodousi, & Bejanpour, 2013, p. 262). Nowadays, the number of components in modern industrial products is so high that managing suppliers has become a serious challenge for manufacturing companies. Supply chain management has therefore brought about significant changes in industrialized countries in the field of production. In this context, the evaluation of industrial buying behavior is also crucial.

Sheth (1973) stated that rational criteria can sometimes influence purchasing behavior. Some of these rational factors include product, company, and personal factors. In uncertain environments, decision-making must sometimes occur with incomplete information (Bevilacqua & Petroni, 2002, p. 236). As Goffin and Marek (1997) indicated, every firm develops its own strategies for managing such uncertainty, which is an important aspect of corporate competitiveness.

Purchasing activity is an essential process in the supply chain. Given the importance of suppliers to product quality and, ultimately, customer satisfaction, organizations must evaluate supplier performance periodically. Many researchers have shown that when organizations fail to evaluate their suppliers regularly, they lose more than 50 % of their opportunities to select the best supplier (Dyer & Chu, 2000).

At the same time, organizations face challenges related to the diversity of indicators used for supplier evaluation across different time periods. They must assess both existing and new suppliers. In today's globalized economy, one of the greatest challenges for industrial organizations is operating in the world market—no economic entity can survive without a

sound strategy. This becomes even more critical when joining the World Trade Organization (WTO) and competing in international markets. Therefore, companies must plan carefully and enhance competition among suppliers of industrial goods.

In large governmental organizations such as the South Pars Gas Complex, several problems exist despite sufficient financial resources and skilled human capital. These include:

1. The entry and inspection of goods;
2. Economic sanctions;
3. Selection criteria in domestic purchasing.

This issue is so significant that companies like the South Pars Gas Complex and its purchasing department conduct research in this area—particularly because of the shared gas fields between Qatar and the Middle East and the focus on revenue generation from these common resources.

Given that there are more than 45,000 types of products involved, the importance of this topic becomes clear. Evaluating appropriate criteria and indicators for supplier assessment and ranking them using methods such as AHP, TOPSIS, and ELECTRE is one of the objectives of this study. In this research, we focus on the business and production divisions of the South Pars Gas Complex to select the best suppliers using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP). One of the strengths of AHP lies in its integration with Multi-Attribute Decision-Making (MADM) methods, providing a more comprehensive evaluation framework. It is not sufficient to focus solely on a single period for supplier selection.

Hamdan and Cheaitou (2015) demonstrated that companies should develop robust mathematical models for supply chain management. Other researchers have also shown that AHP can be effectively used in supplier selection and that MCDM methods can help solve such problems efficiently (Milind & Sharma, 2015, p. 1161). Xu et al. (2013, p. 908) noted

that when a company has an excellent just-in-time process, the supplier selection approach is enhanced through effective decision-making.

Most research findings indicate that there is no universally ideal decision for the supplier selection process—it varies from company to company (De Felice et al., 2015, p. 1). As purchasing factors increase, the importance of this process becomes even more critical (Rajesh & Malliga, 2013, p. 1284). In multi-phase approaches, an initial set of suppliers is identified, followed by qualification, and finally the selection of the best supplier. These two phases—qualification and ranking—are especially important for determining selection criteria (Rezaei, Fahim, & Tavasszy, 2014, p. 8166).

Generally, supplier selection criteria depend heavily on the specific characteristics of each company. Since organizations differ in structure and strategy, obtaining accurate and relevant information for judgment is essential (Deng et al., 2014, p. 156). Many studies have framed their objectives as follows:

- a) To identify various socially responsible supplier selection criteria, sub-criteria, and indicators;
- b) To develop and propose an AHP methodology for selecting socially sustainable suppliers;
- c) To conduct a pilot test in several organizations to validate the AHP model.

Although many studies have relied on the AHP method, in the case of the South Pars Gas Complex, this is the first time that supplier ranking is conducted using the AHP approach. The first well-known research in this field was conducted by Dickson (1966), who distributed a questionnaire containing 32 criteria to 373 American and Canadian managers and employees. They were asked to rank each criterion on a scale from zero (not important) to four (very important).

Importance of Supplier Stance in South Pars Gas Complex

Sales managers and marketers aim to increase inventory and maintain regular supply schedules, while transportation managers, on the other hand, seek to reduce costs by selecting the most efficient transportation methods—even if these processes may take slightly longer.

In previous years, road transportation was the most common method used. However, as the volume of portable goods increased, some companies preferred to purchase their own transport vehicles instead of outsourcing logistics. For certain types of goods, rail transport is considered the best option—especially when time is not a critical factor and cost reduction is a priority. When goods are shipped in large quantities, rail transport or sometimes bulk carriers are more suitable.

For valuable and lightweight goods, air transportation is often the preferred option. Although it is much faster than sea transportation, it is also significantly more expensive. The main costs associated with sea transportation include packaging, loading and unloading, and insurance fees. Regardless of the method chosen, the transportation system should ensure that goods remain safe and undamaged during delivery.

Since the South Pars Gas Complex is geographically distant from major markets for goods and services—located at the southernmost point of the Middle East—transportation represents one of the largest cost components in the total price of delivered goods. These costs can be directly calculated based on the weight or quantity of materials. Therefore, the method of transportation must be carefully analyzed and controlled to manage costs effectively.

Delivery time is another crucial factor in supplier evaluation. Any delay in delivery can cause significant losses to organizations, including production stoppages, increased personnel costs, and contractual penalties. Monitoring on-time delivery performance is also part of meeting quality management standards such as ISO/TS 16949. In many evaluation models, delivery time is used as one of the key performance indicators.

It should also be noted that the geographical distance between the supplier and the refinery is sometimes a critical factor, depending on annual forecasts and production needs. It should also be noted that the geographical distance between the supplier and the refinery is sometimes a critical factor, depending on annual forecasts and production needs. Experts believe that aspects such as the supplier's location, the chosen transportation method, and the quality of communication between the supplier and the company are important in evaluating suppliers.

The Importance of Supplier Reputation for South Pars Gas Complex

The word “brand” originally meant marking an object, such as wood or leather, to show ownership or authenticity. Over time, as markets expanded, the meaning of the word evolved into a concept representing credibility, trust, and influence—the ability of a name or company to affect the behavior of buyers.

The strength and value of a brand reflect its position in the minds and hearts of people. Buyers and consumers usually look for reliable products or services that reduce the risk of purchase while ensuring the best possible results.

In this study, the concept of “brand” is considered through the lens of supplier reputation. Respondents were asked to evaluate how reputation influences supplier

selection by giving scores based on several factors, such as whether the supplier operates globally, is regionally well-known, or focuses mainly on domestic markets. These scores were used in paired comparisons within the questionnaire to assess the importance of supplier reputation for the South Pars Gas Complex.

The Ability and Know-How of Suppliers (According to Records and Previous Performance) for South Pars Gas Complex

In the coming years, industries will increasingly rely on advanced software technologies, moving toward a world with fewer manual workers. Redefining opportunities and responsibilities in such a society—where millions of people may be without formal employment—will become one of the key social challenges of the next century.

One of the most important factors in an organization's performance is the supplier's technical ability and knowledge. The technical capability of suppliers, especially those providing refinery components, was identified in this study as one of the key evaluation criteria.

To measure this factor more accurately, three related indicators were considered: the supplier's warranty provisions, the quality of their staff, and the flexibility of their production line. These sub-criteria help provide a more complete and precise assessment of the supplier's technical ability and know-how.

History of supplier in South Pars Gas Complex

Identifying suppliers and producers of goods and services required to enable the most desirable and highest quality goods with the lowest price and in the quickest possible time by the Investigative Unit resources, based on past purchases the various parts Gas Complex South Pars

is placed. Where are archived in this section include: Company Name, activity diagram, activity description, Phone,

Address, Email, Website, insert date information and the latest issue of purchase that the provider is provided. After the analysis and evaluation of corporate information, categorization of each company according to their records in classified advertising department Order is placed.

It is obvious that a supplier record on previous purchases have an important role in the selection of Avdard. According to past performance in the oil industry as one of the criteria on the desirability of the previous contract is very important. In this study, respondents were asked to provide in relation to the benchmarks experience by taking advantage of convenient assumption for a supplier in your mind, and considering factors such as a history of working with the Ministry of Petroleum, previously cooperated with large companies in other industries score appropriate one to nine for each of the paired comparisons, are recorded in a questionnaire.

Generally, sub-criteria and the technical knowledge of the supplier of the following factors are considered.

- Quality: The quality of materials and services purchased must be free of defects.
- Cost: supplier management and procurement activities should focus on strategic cost management is the process of reducing the total cost of purchasing, transportation, storage, conversion and support products to be considered.
- Time: supplier management and procurement activities and suppliers should play an active role in reducing the time required to deliver new products to market, play.

Technology: supplier management and procurement activities bear the primary responsibility in the field of technology.

Standards and quality certificates

As a supplier with official national or international certificate for each process and each stage of the supply chain, certification, have a clear message to customers and others involved in the industry sends the certificate indicated to implement the necessary standards and consumer demands, committed themselves. This suggests that a maker or supplier of professional quality, safety, competence and efficiency in the production process, packaging and distribution is done. The International Organization for Standardization's ISO concept. Currently, the organization is international, consisting of a network of institutions of national standards in 157 countries worldwide, today ISO standards in production and supply of goods and services is of such importance in the global business arena, ISO initial condition in dealings international is located.

Financial evaluation of large companies such as South Pars in their purchases after receiving the goods, check payable to the vendor issued. It is important that providers be able to pay the cost of its raw materials and the relevant costs. Consultants evaluate the financial strength of suppliers in different companies. One way of assessing the financial power supply based on financial data, is determined to provide a maximum of five years. The maximum score can establish that a sum estimated taxes if the tender is equal to or less than one of the following values:

1. hundred times the average annual tax, documentary paid certain taxes.
2. Twenty-five percent of sales last year of production, based on contracts and sales documents and financial statements certified.
3. Ten percent of fixed assets, based on a formal declaration or certificate of insurance assets.
4. The validity of a bank or financial institution and a valid credit up to the amount of the tender subject.

If the highest number calculated from a sum estimated to be less tender, financial incentives reduced proportionately. In relation to the criteria of financial power suppliers, which the researchers chose these operating factors and sub-criteria (financial position providing funding one supplier), is concerned.

Methodology and Sampling Procedures

In our research, the criteria for the identification of variables were fulfilled, and a questionnaire using a Likert scale was employed. Also, data collection was conducted through a questionnaire, which was distributed to 70 participants, and 55 valid responses were eventually obtained (according to statistical sampling). The first six criteria were identified as the main criteria, and other criteria were selected as sub-criteria associated with the main ones. The second questionnaire contained 28 questions designed for paired comparisons of these criteria.

The questionnaire consisted of two components:

1. Cognitive questions
2. Research questions

Considering the use of theories, principles, and rules that have been developed in fundamental research and their applications to solve real administrative problems, this study is categorized as applied research. It is a descriptive type of study with practical application.

The first questionnaire was designed to identify criteria according to the data and qualitative measures of purchasing agents, which were then expressed quantitatively based on the Likert scale. To analyze and validate the collected data, Excel and SPSS software were used. In the second questionnaire (paired comparisons), the stage of determining results and making the

final decision was carried out using Expert Choice software. This software helps in calculating and ranking decisions based on several different criteria.

The first questionnaire was distributed among 55 experts, and the reliability of their responses was measured using SPSS software with Cronbach's alpha coefficient, which was obtained as 0.806, indicating acceptable reliability. The second questionnaire was distributed among 10 organizations and experts, and the consistency ratio was 0.085, which is acceptable since it is less than 0.1.

The population included directors, officers, and procurement experts of the South Pars Gas Refinery, who are responsible for the procurement of goods. This research was performed in the field of the South Pars Gas Complex, which has more than 1,700 permanent employees and about 3,000 contract workers. Individuals who have an impact on purchasing decisions, and whose decisions play an important role, were considered—approximately 183 people according to organizational charts.

A **simple stratified sampling method** was used, consisting of 55 participants selected from each group. Each group represented members with similar characteristics. After dividing the population into homogeneous groups, each group's sample size was identified, and then, using a simple random sampling method, the required number of participants was selected from each group.

Conceptual Model

In this research, we use the following model:

Figure 2: Conceptual Model

Hypothesis

In order to test the hypothesis and to identify the priorities of the distance, reputation (brand name), financial strength, collaboration resume (with the oil company functions), power and technical knowledge, standards, quality certification providers is the first step of paired comparisons this means that for a couple of factors to be compared on the basis of a criterion. According to data collected by the comments of respondents in the matrix arrays is controversial, according to AkzI and Saati theory for integration of these comments have been using the geometric mean method (technique analysis process group was). In Table 1 of the distance matrix paired comparison, reputation (brand name), financial strength, collaboration resume (with the oil company functions), power and technical knowledge, standards, quality certification for suppliers who achieved arrays of geometric mean method.

Table 1: Paired comparison matrix of criteria for supplier selection (AHP)

	Technical Knowledge	Collaboration Resume	Reputation	Quality	Financial Power	Distance
Technical Knowledge	1	3.213	3.885	0.94	2.54	5.5
Collaboration Resume	0.311	1	2.131	0.27	1.23	4.33
Reputation	0.257	0.469	1	0.22	0.72	2.7
Quality	1.099	3.761	4.577	1	3.22	6.5
Financial Power	0.394	0.814	1.393	0.31	1	3.1
Distance	0.182	0.231	0.371	0.15	0.32	1

In this study, data analysis matrix, and prioritize the factors Excel software and to get the final matrix and the initial calculations and Expert Choice software was used.

Hypothesis 1: It seems that the most important factor in choosing suppliers of industrial goods and refinery is functions of experience working with oil (Collaboration resume).

According to the results, the final weight of supplier partnership record of 0/129 is the amount of weight can operating and technical knowledge (0/297) and standard quality standards (0/344) lower. Therefore, with respect to the rate of inconsistency is acceptable matrix ($0/1 > 0/019$ IR \Rightarrow) the first hypothesis is rejected and cannot be accepted. That history of collaboration with a supplier only in comparison to the distance criteria, reputation and financial strength is more important.

Hypothesis 2: It seems that the least important factor in choosing suppliers of industrial goods and refinery is the distance.

According to the results, the final weight of 040 distance / 0 is the amount of the total weight of the reputation of the supplier (0/079) financial power supplier (0/111), supplier partnership record (0/129), be and knowledge of the supplier (0/297) and standard quality standards (0/344) lower.

Therefore, with respect to the rate of inconsistency is acceptable matrix ($0/1 > 0/019$ IR \Rightarrow) second hypothesis is accepted, ie, that of a provider of distance is the least important compared to other measures.

Hypothesis 3: It seems that the priority of each factor in choosing the suppliers of industrial goods and refinery are different.

According to the results, the final weight of the distance (0/040), the total weight of the reputation of the supplier (0/079), financial power supplier (0/111), supplier partnership record

(0/129), be and knowledge of the supplier (0/297) and standard quality standards (0/344) are different from each other. Therefore, with respect to the rate of inconsistency is acceptable matrix (0/1 > 0/019 IR =) third hypothesis is accepted that the priority of each factor in supplier selection is different.

In the diagram (16 and 17) on the prioritization criteria, the main criteria are, and where Charts, prioritization criteria for supplier selection in the table below is weighted.

Priority on criteria obtained indicates that suppliers of industrial goods should be prioritized for each major criterion in mind. To the proper position in the company's suppliers are considered prioritized list.

Conclusion and results

Selecting the right supplier is of vital importance for the success of a company. Because of this, supplier selection is an vital process of decision making that has an impact on the efficiency of a company. The existence of multiple criteria and more than one participant in the decision making process enables supplier selection to be treated as a multi criteria group decision making problem. Towards a systematic and reasonable method of solving a supplier selection problem, numerous approaches and methods are suggested in literature.

One of the most commonly used methods in many different approaches is AHP. This paper proposes a group decision making approach for supplier selection which consists of a seven step procedure based on the AHP combined with the consensus convergence model and two voting methods: non preferential approval voting and preferential Borda count.

This approach enables quantitative and qualitative criteria to be taken into account and allows more than one decision maker to participate in a process of decision making, which leads to the improvement of the quality of the decision made. The approach combines expert knowledge,

literature data and mathematical procedure, because of which each supplier selection problem can be seen as a distinct decision problem which can be systematically approached, from the defining of the decision problem to the final results of selecting the most appropriate supplier. (Dragin & Vranešević, 2014,787-788)

Purchase as a strategic task that has an effect on the performance of companies, has always been important. Perhaps the most important step of duty Order also related to the selection of suppliers, is appropriate and proper. Therefore, attention must be paid to the participation of all sectors of the draw. In previous models to choose providers, efforts have been made to a similar model for the entire company purchases presented to optimize selection problem. Lack of attention to the specifications of goods purchased one of the major weaknesses of these models in this study, a procedure for consideration of certain characteristics of the goods offered in a choice of suppliers. More effective measures between decision-makers were determined.

For this purpose, an operating model that is used to encompass all aspects of the issue. Goal programming model to consider multiple criteria are used. Since communication is allowed between these criteria and the criteria of importance are different, so the weighted goal programming stage was used. To determine the weighting coefficients and coefficients of qualitative criteria AHP technique was used to resolve the ambiguity of human judgment.

As was anticipated, industrial goods and refinery operating distance or close by seller (supplier) had little importance, and factors such as history of collaboration, the technical and quality standards in products offered far more important for applicants and agents Order was. Supplier Company must satisfy the criteria for their consumer emphasize in Assaluyeh city. What is predicted by many due to the current situation, it was hard it was important to observe quality standards from suppliers. Meanwhile, the partnership records (in past purchases and oil companies operating functions and opinion was more important.

According to the findings, according to the chart rate their importance, it can be concluded that the factors considered in this study, criteria and standards of quality and can provide technical knowledge and the criteria only 4% of distance, and reputation (brand name) 2% there. In the meantime, between the first two criteria, there is a 20% difference with the second criterion; the difference is about 8% for the last two criteria. This result may indicate that differences in scores on criteria related to each criterion in the selection process criteria those considerable extent convenient and preferred suppliers that will affect outcome.

Figure 3. Comparison of Criteria changes (Gap Analysis)

The chart for gap analysis shows that the variation in the priority criteria is up to 0.4 units. This indicates that the main evaluation criteria identified by the decision-makers in the purchasing process are relatively close in importance, and the gap between the lowest and highest priorities is not significant.

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